

Stability of 7-Methylbenzanthrenyl Carbonium Ion

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7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation is found to be very stable and long-lived carbonium ion in concentrated sulfuric acid. When 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol was dissolved in concentrated sulfuric acid a new spectroscopic species appeared which absorbed strongly in the visible region of the spectrum. This species was identified as the carbonium ion. This was revealed in ultraviolet and visible spectra, nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum, and pK_R^+ determination studies of the carbonium ion.

IN view of the potentially interesting chemistry of the carbinol as well as the carbonium ion intermediate derived from it, a study of 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol and 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation was undertaken. We were able to use methylithium in ether to convert benzanthrone to 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol I. 7-methylbenzanthrenyl carbonium ion II was generated from 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol in concentrated sulfuric acid (Fig. 1). The benzanthrenyl cation has been isolated as deep purple perchlorate salt which immediately decomposes on exposure to the atmosphere¹.

Fig. 1. Formation of 7-Methylbenzanthrenyl Cation.

Electronic spectra

Ultraviolet spectrum of 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol I in $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ solution in ethanol shows λ_{max} 222 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2), 229 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.34), 247 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.15), 312 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.11), 328 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.28), and 343 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.25).

Ultraviolet and visible spectra of 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation II in $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $4 \times 10^{-6} M$ solutions in sulfuric acid shows λ_{max} 256 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.9), 283 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 5.14), 357 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0), 408 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.54), 475 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.14) and 565 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.95). The longest wavelength of the alcohol I is 343 nm and longest wavelength of the cation II is 565 nm.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra

NMR spectrum of 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol I in deuterated chloroform shows three peaks, singlet

at δ 1.53 ppm (3 protons of methyl group), singlet at δ 2.45 ppm (1 proton of alcohol) and complex multiplet centered at δ 7.1-8.1 ppm (10 protons of aromatic system).

NMR spectrum of 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation II in concentrated sulfuric acid shows two peaks, singlet at δ 3.55 ppm (3 protons of methyl group) and complex multiplet centered at δ 7.0-8.5 ppm (10 protons aromatic system).

The methyl protons in alcohol I are upfield while methyl protons in cation II are downfield due to the deshielding of the methyl protons by cationic charge.

Determination of pK_R^+

The absorption spectrum of $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ solution of 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol in concentrated sulfuric acid (97%) was determined on Cary 14 spectrophotometer. The absorbance was 0.6 at 475 nm.

In the same manner absorption spectra were determined in 50%, 40%, 35%, 32%, 31% and 30% by volume of sulfuric acid and absorbances were 0.47, 0.45, 0.42, 0.33, 0.30 and 0.22 respectively at 475 nm. At 31% by volume or 41% by weight of sulfuric acid, the absorption was half (0.3) the original absorption (0.6). This means that at this concentration half of the cations have been diminished or destroyed. The pK_R^+ of carbonium ion was determined by using the following equation

$$H_R = pK_R^+ + \log \left(\frac{C_{ROH}}{C_{R^+}} \right)^{2, 3, 5}$$

where

- H_R = Acidity function
- pK_R^+ = Stability of carbonium ion
- C_{R^+} = Concentration of cation
- C_{ROH} = Concentration of carbinol.

The calculated pK_R^+ of the 7-methylbenzanthrenyl carbonium ion turns out to be -4.8 .

Stability of 7-methylbenzanthrenyl carbonium ion

The pK_R^+ of the 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation comes out to be -4.8 and it is half stabilized in 41% sulfuric acid (by weight). These two values $pK_R^+ = -4.8$ and half stabilization in 41% sulfuric acid concentration reflect the stability of 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation compared with other cations in Table 1. In contrast, 9-isopropylxanthyl cation has $pK_R^+ = -1.98$ and it is half stabilized in 15% sulfuric acid³. 1,1-diphenylethyl cation has $pK_R^+ = -10.4$ and it is half stabilized in 75% sulfuric acid³. And 1,1-diphenylpropyl cation has $pK_R^+ = -11.5$ and it is half stabilized in 84% sulfuric acid³.

Lower the value of pK_R^+ and sulfuric acid concentration reflect more stability of the carbonium ion³. 9-Isopropylxanthyl Cation has lowest both values and therefore it is most stable cation. 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation will be more stable than 1,1-diphenylethyl cation and 1,1-diphenylpropyl cation. (Table 1).

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF pK_R^+ VALUES AND STABILITY OF 7-METHYLBENZANTHRENYL CATION

Compound	pK_R^+	% H_2SO_4 where half ionized
9-Isopropylxanthyl Cation ⁴	-1.98	15
7-Methylbenzanthrenyl Cation	-4.8	41
1, 1-Diphenylethyl Cation ⁴	-10.4	75
1, 1-Diphenylpropyl Cation ⁴	-11.5	84

Experimental

Preparation of 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol I

Benzanthrone (10 g), Eastman Kodak, was dissolved in 200 ml of dry ether in the three-necked

flask. An excess (100 ml) of methyllithium (Forte Mineral Company, concentration of CH_3Li in ether 5.08% and 1.67 M) was added by means of hypodermic syringe. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. The lithium salt of the alcohol was hydrolysed by dropwise addition of 100 ml of water by dropping funnel. The alcohol was extracted with ether and combined ether alcohol extracts were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate. Evaporation of ether yielded 8 g (80%) of alcohol which was purified by recrystallization from carbon tetrachloride. The alcohol has melting point of 144.5° . Carbon hydrogen analysis, calcd. C, 87.80%, H, 5.60%. Found : C, 87.89%; H, 5.61%.

Generation of 7-methylbenzanthrenyl cation II

Five ml of concentrated sulfuric acid was taken in a clean dry test tube. 7-methylbenzanthren-7-ol was well ground and then added slowly by means of a spatula to the sulfuric acid test tube. The blood red colour is immediately formed in the sulfuric acid, indicating the formation of the carbonium ion from the alcohol. The colour persists many days, weeks and even months.

References

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